

**THE USE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES
IN IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LESSON**

Makhmuda Kuldasheva

Namangan State University Department of methods of
teaching exact and Natural Sciences in primary education
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8054975>

Annotation. This article covers the importance of the use of virtual presence in the educational system, mechanisms for organizing virtual classes in geography lessons, methods for displaying educational materials, demonstration of materials from atlases, scientific publications from the internet using multimedia tools.

Keywords: educational system, virtual being, illusion, multimedia, virtual lesson, training, individual education, geographic object, comments, text, knowledge comprehension.

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается важность использования виртуального присутствия в системе образования, механизмы организации виртуальных уроков на уроках географии, методы отображения учебного материала, демонстрация материалов из атласов, научных публикаций из интернета с помощью мультимедийных средств.

Ключевые слова: система образования, виртуальное существо, иллюзия, мультимедиа, виртуальный урок, обучение, индивидуальное обучение, географический объект, комментарии, текст, проверка знаний.

The importance of using virtual existence in the educational system lies in the fact that it makes it possible to create on a computer the illusion that a person is acting in real existence. Through this interactive technology, it will be possible to use artificially created computer information through a special interface, computer graphics and sound Media, replacing the perception of objective being with the help of natural sensory organs. Virtual existence is actually something that is practically absent, it is impossible to catch it by hand, to make its taste and smell hiss. But, as it exists, a person enters the fantastic world and not only observes and forgives it, but also has the opportunity to influence it (Table 1).

Table 1. Mechanism for organizing virtual classes in geography lessons

№	Virtual education in science teaching	Virtual education in science teaching
I. Goals, objectives and importance of Education		
1.	The teacher's ability to study the social order of society, which will help them understand the goals and objectives of Geographic Education	The ability to independently (within the framework of hours allotted for independent work) determine the tasks of personal importance of geographical education, depending on the physiological, individual and psychological characteristics of the student
II. Principles of Education		
2.	The teacher's ability to fully implement in practice: the principle of	The ability to choose the speed of mastering the topic when you are in the audience on the computer, get interesting visual materials.

	individualization of education; the principle of visualization-the principle of connecting learning with life	
III. Forms of Education		
3.	<p>Tests and assignments significantly expand the capabilities of the educational system in the audience.</p> <p>Educational research can be done directly without leaving the audience thanks to virtual education</p>	By making decisions about real situations through games, Educational Research, the ability to lose various types of behavior, solving virtual meetings, seminars, Olympiads, test problems-expanding their horizons
4.	Individual education will receive new content and opportunities thanks to virtual education	Creating your own pace of mastering the topic through Individual work.
IV. Content of training		
5.	The ability of the teacher to improve the content of Education:	The ability to obtain current information, study innovations, receive additional information not provided for in textbooks: biographies of researchers, scientists, the variety of visual images of educational material
6.	Correction of the content of education, the choice of methods for presenting geographical material	Brief description of the main topics, excursions to production
V. Teaching methods		
7.	The method of illustration through tables, diagrams, maps located on Internet sites, the demonstration method allows you to show events and processes in dynamics thanks to animation and digital video images. The method of demonstration in teaching"will be able to apply knowledge in everyday activities"	Independently search and change data thanks to various Office programs, Internet sites
8.	Method of studying a	The possibility of systematization and storage

	specific case in Virtual education there are ready-made Developments project method	in various electronic media.
VI. Teaching tools		
9.	The opportunity for the teacher to improve the teaching tools using the following tools:	The ability to choose the most suitable educational tools for yourself. The variety of information education resources allows you to maximally take into account individual interests and opportunities.
10.	Digital educational tools, digital photos, digital videos, animated slideshows, interactive models, games and digital virtual cards	
VII. Control of learning outcomes		
11.	The ability to improve the system of control of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students to the geography teacher.	The ability for the student to choose the degree of difficulty of the test, receive advice if necessary, independently assess the degree of mastery of the geography course, record individual academic performance.

1. Demonstration of educational materials. As a rule, the main visual medium has always been wall-mounted demonstration posters, maps, diagrams, educational films. With the help of Multimedia tools, it is possible to easily display materials from atlases, scientific publications from the internet. They allow students to focus their attention on the most important objects and phenomena depicted on maps and other visual materials[4]. Thus, when studying new material, it is possible to use the product of the company "1C: Education Collection", which provides students with theoretical material in a convenient and visual way. The geography visual weapons library contains several categories of visual materials (henceforth referred to in the text as media objects:

- slides with photographs of certain geographical objects with text comments (for example, a photo of a sample of natural processes, geopolitical processes, iceberg, volcano, etc.);
- slides with photos of the results of the event with a specific geographical process, text comments (for example, photos of houses destroyed after an earthquake);
- slides with diagrams, diagrams, tables, reflecting the structure of geographical objects, the essence of geographical phenomena and processes, their qualitative and quantitative characteristics (for example, a stratovolcano structure diagram, a table, describing the dynamics of the world population, etc.);
- videos that reflect geographic processes or events with text comments (e.g. decline and flow);
- animations when they are displayed, geographic processes and phenomena are modeled (e.g., changes in the state political map, economic ties), with textual comments;

- diagram maps with interactive maps and text comments.

2. Knowledge verification: the use of computer programs (tests, OMS, MAMI TESTING) designed for automated verification of the level of knowledge and skills. 3. When organizing independent work of students: - to select the necessary information; - to study new educational material; - to carry out practical work; - to create "own" products of educational activities: notes, abstracts, projects, etc.; - to develop skills and qualifications;- to prepare for competitions, Olympiads; - to carry out educational and research work.

We can travel through the virtual world to some country or sea, walk there in various entertainment alleys of cities, get acquainted with the industrial enterprise, drive a car released in car factories or bathe in the sea.but the virtual world does not give a person pleasure, like a real physical being[6]. The reason is, the sensations that arise under the influence of this being are realized in many ways not by him himself, but through how we perceive and imagine.

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that virtual existence is currently used in the sphere and branches of human cultural activity. Above all, it is used in the field in which it occurs, in science, including in physics, modeling the dynamics of liquids and gases, in chemistry, in the construction of a model of chemical reactions, in geology and geography, in the modeling of card schemes, relief and volcanoes, and samasadorism is achieved.

References:

1. Sh.Mirziyoyev "new Uzbekistan strategy" Tashkent.The year 2021
2. Bent B.Andresen and Katja van den Brink. Multimedia in Education.UNESCO Institute for Information Technologis in Education. 2013.ISBN 978-5-7777-0556-3.p.3
3. Davidov, V.V., Uchebnaya deyatelnost I modelirovanie. / [Tekst] / V.V. Davidov, A.He. Vardanyan-Yerevan: Luys, 1981. - 219s.
4. Cecília Sík Lányi. VIRTUAL REALITY AND ENVIRONMENTS.First published April, 2012. Printed in Croatia. Published by InTech.ISBN 978-953-51-0579-4, p.31
5. Vahobov H., M.Tillaboeva. Fundamentals of economic geography. (teacher's book) - Tashkent. Teacher, 2001. - B. 4-5
- 6.Drapeau Patti. Sparking student creativity (practical ways to promote innovative thinking and problem cooling). – Alexandria-Virginia, USA: ASCD, 2014.- R. 4.
7. Komilova N., Jumakhanov Sh. "Methodology of economic and social geography".Textbook. "University" 2020. P. 46
8. Chorley R.DJ. P.Model V geografii.M.: Progress, 1971. 78th s
9. <https://hadoop.apache.org/>
10. <http://spatialhadoop.cs.umn.edu/>
11. <https://registry.opendata.aws>
12. Mahmudova M. D., Quldasheva M. N. using from the leading innovational methods in teacing on the theme "social-economical groups of the world countries", the political map of the world at the present time //Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology. – 2019. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 270-275.
13. Nurmatjonovna Q. M. ISSUES OF ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS IN THE SUBJECT OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL GEOGRAPHY //Conferencea. – 2022. – C. 14-19.

14. Juraevna M. M., Nurmatjonovna Q. M. Methods And TECHNOLOGY Of Teaching Economic And Social Geography //METHODS. – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 12.
15. Nurmatjonovna Q. M. TOPICAL ISSUES OF USING INTERACTIVE TECHNIQUES IN GEOGRAPHY //Conferencea. – 2022. – С. 48-52.
16. Kuldasheva M. N. THE USE OF ACTIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT «WORLD ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL GEOGRAPHY» //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 11. – С. 437-439.
17. Кулдашева М. Н. Использование нестандартных тестов на уроках географии //География в школе. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 33-37.
18. Кулдашева М. Н. АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ТЕМЫ ДЛЯ ОБОГАЩЕНИЯ СОДЕРЖАНИЯ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ГЕОГРАФИИ //Conferencea. – 2023. – С. 175-180.
19. Кулдашева М. Н., Махмудова М. Ж. ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ВЫБОРА ОБУЧАЮЩИХ МЕТОДОВ НА УРОКАХ МИРОВОЙ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ГЕОГРАФИИ THE TECHNOLOGY OF CHOOSING TEACHING METHODS IN ECONOMICAL AND SOCIAL GEOGRAPHY LESSONS IN THE WORLD //ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ ВЕКТОРЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ И СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА. – 2019. – С. 69.
20. Nurmatjonovna K. M. MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF PERSONALITY-ORIENTED EDUCATION //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.
21. Nurmatjonovna Q. M. TOPICAL ISSUES OF USING INTERACTIVE TECHNIQUES IN GEOGRAPHY //Conferencea. – 2022. – С. 48-52.
22. Madinabonu, Y. . (2023). Comparative Analysis of Korean Animalistic Fairy Tales. Miasto Przyszłości, 31, 373–377.
23. Madinabonu, Y. . (2023). Analysis of the Korean Fairy Tale Konji-Patji. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(1), 189–193.
24. Rahimjanovna, S. M. . (2023). Primary Class' Technology as a Creative Subject. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(1), 84–87.
25. Shermatova, M. R. . (2023). Continuity of Education and Education in Technology. AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT, 2(1), 213–217.
26. Shermatova, M. R. . (2023). Spiritual Wealth Education of Students in the National Spirit through. Miasto Przyszłości, 31, 396–400.